

Quantum Oscillator, Statistics and Phase Space Considerations

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In a previous note, we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution follows from the maximization of uncertainty in momentum space (i.e. every p, x point can be discerned or the number of degenerate cells in a phase space volume with energy $=e_i \gg n(e_i)$). For the Bose-Einstein (and also the Fermi-Dirac case), the uncertainty principle (and for fermions the exclusion principle) coarse grain phase space into a lower number of degenerate cells (such that g_i is not $\gg n(e_i)$). Each point p, x is no longer discernible. From these ideas, one may derive the MB, BE and FD distributions by maximizing arrangements in the degenerate boxes subject to: $\sum_i n(e_i) = N$ and $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E$ total. In this note, we attempt to apply these ideas to a quantum wavefunction without temperature. For example, for the ground state harmonic oscillator $W_0(x) = C \exp(-ax^2)$ and $f(p) = \exp(-bp^2)$. In both cases, these match the Maxwell-Boltzmann result for the oscillator, but for other quantum cases there is no such match. We argue that for the ground state quantum oscillator wavefunction, the distribution of p and x is "random" (i.e. there is full maximization of uncertainty and this matches the Maxwell-Boltzmann situation. For other quantum cases, even the excited oscillator, we argue there are correlations (i.e. p and x are no longer "random"). For example, an excited oscillator absorbs a phonon which has a distinct frequency which seems to break the randomness of the ground state scenario (even though the ground state also has a frequency).

Quantum Mechanics and Statistical Mechanics

Quantum mechanics and statistical mechanics are both statistical theories, but in general are treated separately. For example, the quantum wavefunction satisfies an equation such as the Schrodinger equation and for the nonrelativistic case $W(x)^* W(x)$ yields a spatial probability distribution while $f^*(p) f(p)$ from $W(x) = \sum_p f(p) \exp(ipx)$, a momentum probability distribution. Statistical mechanics, on the other hand, seems to be based on phase space $d^3p dV / h^3$. This phase space unit may be thought of as consisting of $g(e_i)$ degenerate cells, each with the same energy e_i . In classical physics, each momentum and position vector is resolvable and so one may argue that $g(e_i)$ is very large in fact $g(e_i) \gg n(e_i)$. In the quantum case, there is much less resolution due to the uncertainty relationship (or other causes) and $g(e_i)$ and $n(e_i)$ are treated on "equal" footing. Thus, in statistical mechanics, a temperature equilibrium is created. The potential simply serves to change kinetic energy into potential energy, but the thermal equilibrium is still present. In quantum mechanical single particle wavefunctions, the potential seems to be responsible for scattering $\exp(ipx)$ waves and a resonance is formed, with E as a frequency.

Let us examine the statistical mechanical case for quantum particles. For example, for fermions, only one fermion may be in a quantum state. Thus, if there is a degeneracy of $g(e_i)$ one maximizes:

$\ln \left[\frac{g(e_i)!}{[n(e_i)! (g(e_i) - n(e_i))!]} \right]$ subject to $\sum_i n(e_i) = N$ and $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ ((1))

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $g(e_i) \gg n(e_i)$ so one essentially has $\ln(n(e_i))$ with the same constraints.

For the boson case, one maximizes:

$\ln \left[\frac{(g(e_i) - 1 + n(e_i))!}{[n(e_i)! (g(e_i) - 1)!]} \right]$ subject to the same constraints ((2))

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $g(e_i) \gg n(e_i)$ and ((2)) reduces to $\ln[n(e_i)!]$.

Thus, the distinction between the quantum (temperature) statistical situation and the classical (MB) temperature case seems to be the number of degenerate cells in phase space compared to $n(e_i)$.

A quantum wavefunction for a single particle (with no temperature), however, is also a statistical object. One may ask: Do the phase space resolution issues described above apply at all to a single particle ($T=0$) wavefunction? In this note, we try to argue that there may be a connection.

Single Particle Quantum Wavefunction

A single particle quantum wavefunction $W(x)$ is a statistical object. We consider bound state wavefunctions here for which $W(x)W(x)$ yields the spatial probability distribution and $f_p f_p$, where $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$, the momentum distribution. Every point x and p may be "used" in the equation, but the particle's overall position and momentum are uncertain i.e. one may calculate a variance which may be used in the uncertainty principle. Even for a particle in a box with a wavefunction $\sin(kx)$, all momentum p values are involved, k is only the average momentum (i.e. one needs to take the Fourier transform of the step function at the box walls).

The wavefunction is the solution of a differential equation. For the nonrelativistic case (without spin considerations) one may use the Schrodinger equation which usually has a potential $V(x)$. Thus, even though $W(x)$ is statistical over all x and all p , there are constraints due to the Schrodinger equation. In one special case, however, namely the ground state of a harmonic oscillator, something "unusual" happens, namely $W(x)W(x) = C \exp(-ax^2)$ and $f_p f_p = C^2 \exp(-bp^2)$ where C , C^2 , a and b are constants. These distributions are of the same form as the classical Maxwell-Boltzmann case, but the MB case is based on the idea of there being complete uncertainty in phase space (with all of phase space being resolvable). We suggest this may be the same case for the ground state oscillator. The Gaussian distribution in general seems to suggest complete randomness, which may explain why the classical statistical case and the quantum case coincide in this one situation.

For higher energy oscillator solutions, the link between quantum statistics and classical is broken. The oscillator, however, is excited by adding a phonon which has a distinct frequency and a structured wavefunction. Thus, it seems the randomness may be broken. For all other

$V(x)$ cases, ground state or not, it seems a complete randomness of p and x (following a Gaussian distribution) no longer occurs and so the link between classical statistics and the quantum single particle wavefunction is no longer present.

Quantum Mechanical Single Particle Wavefunction as a Resonance

It was argued in previous notes that the single particle wavefunction in the Schrodinger equation is involved in a resonance. For example, one may write:

$$\int dp \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j = E \int dp f_p \quad ((3))$$

Here $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$.

The same E holds for all p , thus all $\exp(ipx)$ seem to be part of a resonance with the same frequency E . Even the ground state oscillator has this resonance which is driven by $V(x)$.

On the other hand, the Schrodinger equation (in 1D $\hbar=1$) for the oscillator may be written as:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + \frac{1}{2} k x^2 W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Or } \frac{1}{2} m p^2 f_p - \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dp} \frac{d}{dp} f_p = E f_p$$

Thus, f_p and $W(x)$ should have the same form, furthermore a Gaussian is one solution (for both f_p and $W(x)$).

Thus, it is possible, in one case, to have "random" Gaussian distributions for x and p for a single particle which satisfies a Schrodinger equation, namely the ground state of an oscillator. We argue this randomness is identical to maximizing uncertainty in phase space for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. In the classical case, the MB weight factor is $\exp(-E/T)$. For an oscillator, a particle with momentum p_1 at x_1 with energy $E = p_1^2/2m + \frac{1}{2} k x_1^2$ is equivalent to p_2 at x_2 such that $E = p_2^2/2m + \frac{1}{2} k x_2^2$. Thus, the "Gaussian randomness" is the same for both x and p . Without a potential, one has $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$, which treats all x points as the same. This is "complete" uncertainty in x as well, but there is no resonance link (which is needed for the quantum Schrodinger equation).

Thus, in the quantum ground state, there is "randomness", i.e. a Gaussian for both $W(x)$ and $f(p)$ because there must be a link between kinetic and potential energy due to the Schrodinger equation.

Non-Oscillator Ground State Solutions

One may ask why excited oscillator and Schrodinger equation solutions for other $V(x)$ do not mimic classical statistical mechanics. We argue that classical statistical mechanics is based on

randomizing phase space (based on number and energy constraint). In the case of a potential, one still randomizes phase space, but $E=p^2/2m$ at x_1 such that $V(x_1)=0$ has the same probability as p_2 at x_2 where $V(x_2)$ is not zero i.e. $\exp(-p_1^2/2mT) = \exp(-p_2^2/2mT + V(x_2))$.

The Schrodinger equation, on the other hand, does not randomize phase space, it rather tries to create a resonance of $\exp(ipx)$ type objects (which add as amplitudes with different weights) with the resonance being related to kinetic and potential energy. The potential energy is responsible for scattering one $\exp(ip_1x)$ into another $\exp(ip_2x)$, but this has to occur in such a way that a resonance is created, with the same frequency for all $\exp(ipx)$. For statistical mechanics, there is also scattering of different particles (as in the oscillator), but one randomizes this scattering subject to constraints to create a temperature resonance. The potential simply changes the kinetic energy from one point to another, it does not seem to create the thermal resonance. For the case of the ground state oscillator, the Schrodinger equation has a solution for which $f_p \cdot f_p$ is randomized (exactly in the manner of maximizing phase space) and by the nature of the Schrodinger equation $W(x)$ has the same form.

Thus, it seems that when comparing classical Maxwell-Boltzmann type statistics to quantum mechanical single particle wavefunctions, the following applies. MB statistics maximizes randomness (i.e. number of arrangements) in phase space (where every point is discernable or resolvable) subject to constraints on energy and particle number. This yields $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. If f_p is also of this form, is it possible for f_p to still be a solution of the Schrodinger equation? The answer appears to be yes, in the case of the ground state of the harmonic oscillator.

Interparticle Scattering Versus Inter- $\exp(ipx)$ Scattering

For the quantum case, interparticle scattering is enhanced or restricted for bosons and fermions due to the lack of resolution in phase space. For bosons:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ and } f(e_1)[1 + f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1 + f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1 + f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1 + f(e_2)]$$

While for fermions: $f(e_1)[1 - f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1 - f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1 - f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1 - f(e_2)]$

In the case of $\exp(ipx)$ “waves” scattering as part of a single particle wavefunction, there does not seem to be a lack of resolution in phase space. For the case of the oscillator ground state, the momentum probability distribution $\exp(-ap \cdot p)$ matches that of the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which all of phase space is discernible. It is interesting the resolution of all p and x within a single particle wavefunction, but that this function leads to an overall variance of x and p for the particle, which has an effect on multi-particle scattering and occupation in phase space (when trying to create a quantum temperature statistical mechanics). Thus, among quantum particles, there is not full resolution of phase space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue statistical mechanics deals with maximizing randomness in phase space. For the MB case, all phase space points are discernible, while for the Bose-Einstein and

Fermi-Dirac, they are not (due to the uncertainty principle). The MB result for the nonrelativistic case is $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. Quantum mechanics is also a statistical theory, but is not based on maximizing randomness in phase space. Rather, it seems to focus on forming a resonance of $\exp(ipx)$ objects which are scattered in a potential. The resonance is described by a Schrodinger equation with a solution of $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ of } \exp(ipx)$. If one asks whether it is possible to have a solution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$, or $\exp(-p^2)$, one finds that the ground state harmonic oscillator is such a case, although it is essentially the only one. We argue, however, that the idea of the p 's being randomly distributed subject to the energy constraint seems to apply to both Maxwell-Boltzmann statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics in this one case. It is interesting that for the $\exp(ipx)$ waves which make up the single particle wavefunction, there can be complete phase space resolution, but among different quantum mechanical particles, this resolution is lost because of the uncertainty principle.

References

Ruggeri, Francesco R. Phase Space Uncertainty in Quantum Mechanics and the Bose-Einstein Distribution (preprint, zenodo, 2020)